

Optimization of urban morphology to enhance outdoor thermal comfort: A microclimate analysis

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Abstract

Climate-aware urban environments pose a significant imperative to obtain thermally comfortable outdoor areas. The present study addresses the optimization of urban block morphology in Guelma City, Algeria, to enhance thermal performance in a semi-arid climate. Using in-situ measurements and simulation generated by the ENVI-met simple forcing scheme, the impact of urban morphology on the variation of outdoor comfort factors, including air temperature, relative humidity, and wind speed parameters, is identified. The conducted investigation illustrates building configuration, orientation, and street canyon geometry as key indices affecting thermal comfort. Results pointed out urban green cover's role in mitigating heat island effects. In conclusion, the study underscored the significance of an interconnected analysis of urban patterns and their correlated influence on urban microclimate for achieving thermally comfortable outdoor environments.

Key words: ENVI-met simulation, thermal perception, urban heat stress, urban spatial configuration

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1. Introduction

Urban climate has emerged as a primary area of inquiry, mainly due to the growth of urbanization and climate change's dramatic surge. These synchronized occurrences have considerably compromised environmental balance and the quality of outdoor space, leading to an intensified urban heat island (UHI) effect characterized by elevated temperature levels within cities (Bourikas et al. 2013; Iamtrakul et al. 2024).

The urgency of climate change demands the implementation of effective climatic evaluation methods (Chatzinikolaou et al. 2018). The relevant methods require a deep understanding of the meteorological factors within the context of urban microclimate analysis, as it encompasses the immediate environment, which affects the inhabitant's comfort the most (Yang et al. 2023). Recent multifaceted studies highlight the intricate connection between outdoor thermal comfort, urban geography, and architecture (Dunjić 2019; Asa and Zemba 2023; Mperejekumana et al. 2024; Ofremu et al. 2024). Technological advancements,

such as Geographic Information Systems (GIS) and remote sensing, have facilitated urban climate analysis and its relevance to thermal comfort (Frimpong et al. 2023; Kasniza Jumari et al. 2023). Moreover, nature-based solutions, including green urbanism, have been emphasized to mitigate urban planning impacts on climate (Jarosińska and Gołda 2020; Santos et al. 2021; Jabbar et al. 2022).

Multiple parameters can significantly determine thermal sensation; air temperature (AT) emerges as the most significant parameter to affect outdoor thermal perception (Liu et al. 2016; Ranagalage et al. 2018; Mahmoud et al. 2021; Garcia Izquierdo et al. 2024). However, conducting a comprehensive assessment of thermal comfort necessitates the inclusion of two additional parameters, which are relative humidity (RH) and wind speed (W) (Yang et al. 2023). Moreover, the urban environment, characterized by its physical characteristics such as building layout and density (Othman and Alshboul 2020; Aboelata 2021), street canyon geometry and orientation (Shishegar 2013; Disanayake et al. 2021; Abdollahzadeh and Bioria 2021; Abd Elraouf et al. 2022), and urban green spaces (Lee et al. 2016; Hami et al. 2019; Oquendo-Di Cosola et al. 2022; Wang et al. 2024), exerts a significant influence on the distribution of thermal metrics (Maleki et al. 2014). Thus, the spatial configuration of the built environment (Darbani et al. 2023) plays a crucial role in shaping thermal conditions and climate stability (Oke 1988; Arnfield 2003; Tapias and Schmitt 2014; Mahmoud and Ragab 2020).

Numerous studies have investigated the impact of urban morphology on local climate. For instance, research by (Liu et al. 2021) in Beijing demonstrated the influence of urban spatial layout on the UHI effect, ventilation, and urban discomfort index (UDI) more than other urban parameters. Similarly, Zhang et al. (2022) quantified the impact of urban spatial configuration on local thermal comfort in complex urban areas. Another study by (Boukhabla et al. 2013) explored the impact of urban morphology on the AT variation of urban conditions in the hot and dry climate of Biskra City in Algeria. These papers highlight the impact of building design on outdoor conditions and emphasize the importance of urban design in mitigating heat-related issues and achieving thermal comfort.

Consequently, multiple strategies and approaches have been developed in response to outdoor comfort optimization. Those strategies incorporate the use of questionnaire surveys (Sharmin and Steemers 2020), field measurement (Liu et al. 2022), and numerical modeling (Tumini et al. 2016; Limona et al. 2019). Additionally, numerous studies have succeeded in combining in-situ measurements and simulation approaches (Gusson and Duarte 2016; Mahmoud et al. 2021; Sun et al. 2022; Al Haddid and Al-Obaidi 2022; Deng et al. 2023; Brahim et al. 2023; Wang et al. 2024).

The increasing rate of international research on climate change mitigation (Ouyang et al. 2022; Mishra and Sadhu 2023; Kotharkar and Dongarsane 2024) emphasizes the necessity to clarify the correlation between urban design patterns and thermal comfort in Algerian cities. Therefore, this study employs a coupling evaluation methodology to investigate urban geometry's impact on the thermal characteristics of outdoor spaces in Guelma City. The study focuses on essential environmental parameters, particularly AT, RH, and W, aiming to contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of the influence of urban form on the perception of thermal sensation in outdoor environments.

2. Materials and methods

The study incorporates a two-phased methodological framework. The initial phase consists of data collection and model generation. The physical morphology is analyzed by bringing together several main aspects using available parameters, including building form, construction material type, urban density, street canyon and orientation, and distribution of vegetation. Based on this analysis, a three-dimensional model is constructed utilizing the collected data. The generated model, obtained from the urban morphological analysis, permits visualization of building behavior to external influences.

The second phase encompasses environmental simulation and examination. Three meticulously chosen case studies, each featuring distinct urban layouts within similar climatic conditions, were used for comparison. The purpose was to compare the performance of different urban morphologies towards climate conditions. A microclimate simulation ENVI-met software is utilized to simulate the environmental features within the established model. The simulation employs air temperature, relative humidity, and wind speed data for both hot and cold periods.

Figure 1. Optimization framework.

Fig. 1 denotes the optimization framework of the aforementioned phases, centering on parametric modeling and simulation examination. The urban configuration model is constructed utilizing the AutoCAD two-dimensional scheme to perform a three-dimensional model via the ENVI-met spaces tool. To collect microclimate parameters, field measurements were carried out to provide accurate meteorological data related to the local climatic region used in the initial phase. A Dew Point Hygrometer and an Anemometer model BA16 instruments, discussed in detail in the meteorological data section, are employed. This data serves as input for the ENVI-guide tool to prepare for urban weather generation. Following the simulation, a data analysis approach was conducted to visualize and assess the optimization criteria.

The research’s optimization process is implemented through a data-driven and simulation-based approach. The purpose was to elucidate the complex interaction between urban spatial configuration and outer spaces’ thermal efficiency. The process core is to optimize urban morphology by fostering a synergistic interplay between climate change mitigation, environmental comfort, and the building form. The research establishes a comprehensive framework to prioritize climate-adaptive urban configuration and achieve urban climate resilience.

2.1. Case study

The study was conducted in Guelma City, the capital of Guelma Province, Algeria, situated in the northeastern part at coordinates 36.47°N and 7.47°E, roughly 65 km from the Mediterranean coast and characterized by a semi-arid climate according to the Algerian climatic classification. The selected area for this study concentrates on the new district of Guelma, also referred to as the South land occupancy plan (POS).

The exact location of Guelma City within Algeria is presented in Fig. 2. This figure provides a clear understanding of the city’s geographical context, particularly its orientation and climatic zone, important factors influencing the case study.

Figure 2. Geographic location of the study area. **A** Location of Guelma City within the territory of Algeria **B** Location of the South POS within Guelma City **C** Case study area (Google Earth 2024).

The examination was carried out considering several factors, including building geometry, street canyon and orientation, urban density, construction materials, and vegetation distribution.

Fig. 3 illustrates the urban built environment of the studied area with a designation of the materials used in the building surfaces as well as ground material, providing a detailed view of the surrounding area. The mapping figure helps to identify key urban parameters that need to be taken into consideration during the analysis process.

Based on the predetermined selection, three different geometrical configurations with distinct characteristics were extracted for modeling purposes. The objective is to analyze the behavior of various structures to weather external variations.

Figure 3. Urban built environment of the study area.

Table 1 screens the extracted urban spatial configurations and details the characteristics of each building block. These characteristics include building form, vegetation cover distribution, block height, urban canyon, and orientation.

Table 1. Description of the case study blocks.

Characterization	Building blocks		
Orientation	North-south	North-south	East-west
Urban typology	Courtyard typology	Linear typology	Linear typology
Vegetation cover	Melia tree	Natural soil	Natural soil
Building height (m)	Mid-rise 22.8	Mid-rise 19.2	Mid-rise 19.2
Urban canyons (m)	8	27	18
Wall material	Concrete		
Roof material	Concrete		
Cooling system	Air conditioner		
Heating system	Gas		

2.2. Meteorological data

In-situ measurements were conducted at the same location to assess the climatological conditions within the research area. The specific location included urban geometries with varying vegetation cover. Air temperature, relative humidity, and wind speed measurements were operated employing specific instruments. These instruments were a Dew Point Hygrometer for AT and RH calculation and an Anemometer model BA16 for quantifying wind speed. The measurements were carried out at regular intervals (8:00 a.m., 12:00 p.m., and 4:00 p.m.) during both hot and cold seasons.

The selected instruments were held at a height of 1.7 m and oriented towards the sun to ensure accurate solar radiation measurements. These devices can measure both minimum and maximum values of weather metrics by pressing the holder button and switching between regular, minimum, and maximum modes. In minimum mode, the device continuously recorded the lowest value of the weather metric until the button was pressed again. In maximum mode, the device recorded the highest value until the button was pressed. This process allowed for the collection of both the average and extreme values of weather metrics, providing a comprehensive understanding of the microclimatic conditions within the study area.

Tables 2, 3 capture the recorded thermal variations of the studied area for the months of August and February. These tables present the variations in weather factors according to different timeframes to highlight the differences between the two seasons. Although the selection of two months does not encompass the microclimate patterns throughout the year, it was sufficient to provide a valuable initiation to the difference in the microclimatic conditions between summer and winter. Significantly, the meteorological data collection process took into consideration the potential impact of vegetation cover, as revealed in Table 4, by recording measurements under the present trees in the located urban geometries.

Table 2. Thermal comfort assessment of the relevant hot period. AT = air temperature; RH = relative humidity; W = wind speed.

		AT (°C)			RH (%)			W (m/s)		
		8 ^h	12 ^h	16 ^h	8 ^h	12 ^h	16 ^h	8 ^h	12 ^h	16 ^h
August, 1st	Min	20.70	39.90	32.90	56.20	35.70	37.90	00.57	00.80	00.87
	Max	27.20	46.00	34.90	57.60	36.90	39.00	00.77	00.94	01.10
August, 2nd	Min	27.00	36.60	36.40	62.70	34.20	34.40	00.47	01.00	01.01
	Max	27.60	38.90	37.80	63.40	33.50	35.20	00.86	01.90	01.88
August, 3rd	Min	29.40	40.60	38.90	48.70	25.80	26.90	00.00	00.00	01.72
	Max	32.90	42.00	39.60	49.70	26.40	27.70	00.88	00.75	01.95

Table 3. Thermal comfort assessment of the relevant cold period.

		AT (°C)			RH (%)			W (m/s)		
		8 ^h	12 ^h	16 ^h	8 ^h	12 ^h	16 ^h	8 ^h	12 ^h	16 ^h
Feb, 24th	Min	10.70	15.80	10.90	70.50	32.90	55.50	00.02	00.78	02.86
	Max	11.10	16.30	12.40	71.30	34.00	60.20	00.09	03.08	08.12
Feb, 25th	Min	09.00	14.50	15.40	68.90	43.70	38.50	02.05	01.32	02.04
	Max	09.20	14.90	15.80	69.50	44.40	39.90	04.59	03.48	06.01
Feb, 29th	Min	08.60	10.40	09.80	74.50	90.80	83.90	02.22	00.98	01.08
	Max	08.80	10.50	10.20	75.20	91.60	87.40	08.17	01.83	04.07

Table 4. Thermal comfort assessment of the relevant hot period under masking effect (vegetation).

		AT (°C)			RH (%)			W (m/s)		
		8 ^h	12 ^h	16 ^h	8 ^h	12 ^h	16 ^h	8 ^h	12 ^h	16 ^h
August, 1st	Min	19.80	34.90	32.80	26.10	37.20	19.55	00.00	00.00	00.00
	Max	20.70	37.60	35.00	29.40	36.90	22.00	00.10	00.30	00.22
August, 2nd	Min	26.00	36.20	29.20	61.20	17.70	18.60	00.00	00.00	00.00
	Max	27.00	37.00	32.70	63.50	18.80	19.50	00.20	00.80	00.75
August, 3rd	Min	28.40	37.80	38.50	18.40	26.80	27.90	00.00	00.00	00.00
	Max	30.80	38.50	39.00	19.70	31.80	29.00	00.20	00.70	01.45

2.3. Software and parametric modeling

2.3.1. Software selection criteria

Despite the advancements in using instruments for microclimate analysis, obtaining accurate outcomes could be difficult to achieve due to the complex connection of the built environment parameters (Detommaso et al. 2021). Weather patterns and the wide variances of the urban geometry impose significant limitations regarding purely empirical microclimatic studies, such as a simple on-site collection of weather data (Bourikas et al. 2013). Therefore, using simulation is an essential process that has a recognized role to ensure the reliability of a model and obtain precise visualization of findings (Matott et al. 2009).

ENVI-met software has emerged as one of the leading programs to perform outdoor thermal comfort analysis. The software offers exceptional accuracy in evaluating meteorological conditions through a grid-based model (Tsoka et al. 2018; Mahmoud et al. 2021; Wang et al. 2024; Liu et al. 2024). This accuracy is fostered by its efficiency in simulating a complex combination of various elements, including building geometry, vegetation, urban patterns, and weather parameters. Additionally, ENVI-met is recognized for its user-friendly interface that offers efficient simulation runs for researchers and users, enabling the acquisition of results within a short timeframe. Furthermore, one of the valuable features of ENVI-met is simulating different scenarios, which allows comparison of findings (ENVI-Met 2024).

The performance of ENVI-met simulations has been assessed through several studies. In comparison with in-situ measurement data, Yang et al. (2013) examined the thermal behavior of different ground surfaces to local temperature and humidity in southern China, validating ENVI-met effectiveness in analyzing urban thermal environments in hot-humid climates. Further research by Crank et al. (2020) conducted a comparative analysis to test the program's applicability in diverse urban forms. Findings emphasized the importance of in-situ support data for quantifying potential errors. Expanding on the software capabilities, Lee et al. (2016), Chatzinikolaou et al. (2018), and Sayad et al. (2021) investigated the ability of urban elements, such as vegetation, to improve thermal comfort conditions in the urban environment. In addition, Ouyang et al. (2022) reported in their study on thermal-radiative performance of the ENVI-met model that the software achieved the most accurate results. In conclusion, these studies underscored the effectiveness of ENVI-met as a tool for analyzing urban thermal environments.

2.3.2. Urban climate modeling and simulation

The objective of this phase is to analyze the impact of urban form factors on outdoor thermal comfort. The microclimate modeling and simulation process, which occurred on the 7th, 21st, and 25th of March 2024, was generated using the latest version of ENVI-met software (ENVI-met 5.5.1), which facilitates data preparation and model configuration.

The general modeling and simulation workflow via ENVI-met, presented in Fig. 4, illustrates using area parameters and meteorological data to serve as input data for the ENVI-met model. This input data included a two-dimensional representation in a bitmap file (.bmp) of the study area, preprocessed in AutoCAD software based on a map data capture view.

The two-dimensional model incorporated building shapes and orientation, street canyons, and distribution of vegetation according to a specified grid size of 50x50x40 pixels/grid with a resolution (Δx and Δy) of 2 m. To generate the three-dimensional model, ENVI-met provides an articulated set of tools for defining various urban elements within the model, including building heights, construction materials for walls and roofs, street layouts, open spaces, and a diverse range of plant types. Each of these elements was chosen in accordance with the built environment of the case study. Following the development of the three-dimensional model, ENVI-met generated an area output file in an ENVI-met Area Input File (INX) format.

Figure 4. General modeling and simulation workflow via ENVI-met.

The subsequent phase entails environmental simulation and examination, which necessitate the inclusion of meteorological data. This data can be manually entered or imported from a weather file stored in the comma-separated values (.CSV) format. A crucial step during model initialization for simulation is the selection of a forcing scheme for the meteorological boundary conditions. While a full forcing scheme represents the highest level of precision, it requires more information regarding the surrounding meteorological conditions, for instance, cloud amount, precipitation, and radiation levels. Given these data demands, a simple forcing scheme was employed for this particular model.

To understand the ENVI-met modeling and simulation process, Table 5 details the specific meteorological boundary conditions employed in the model generation. The initial phase involves configuring the software environment, defining the model location, and preparing necessary data sets to digitize and build the three-dimensional model. Urban spatial morphology parameterization focuses on detailed building parameters, including building dimensions, materials, and external configurations. The model is meticulously constructed to accurately represent the existing environment for reliable results. The second phase imported weather data, including AT, RH, and W, for simulating atmospheric conditions using ENVI-guide. The simulation parameter settings and meteorological data were defined at this stage. The model, incorporating weather data, is subjected to a simulation process to predict environmental conditions in an ENVI-met Simulation Task (SIMX) file. The SIMX file serves as input for the core simulation engine, ENVI-core. Following the run by ENVI-core simulation, results are presented visually through the ENVI-met visualization tool Leonardo, which facilitates visualization of the simulation results by generating detailed maps. The provided maps were generated at specific heights to illustrate the effect of vegetation cover on weather variables.

Table 5. Simulation parameters setting.

Modeling settings	Model location	36°36'37"N 7°26'05"E
	Rotation of grid north	0.00
	Grid cell (m)	dx=2 dy=2 dz=2
	Wall material	Default wall
	Roof material	Default wall
	Input file	(.bmp)
	Road	Asphalt
	Pavement	Concrete (used)
Simulation parameter setting	Simulation date	07/03/2024
	Simulation duration	10 (h)
	Meteorological boundary conditions	Simple forcing
	Boundary conditions	Grid (50x50x40)
	Time of air temperature max/min	12h / 8h
	Time of relative humidity max/min	8h / 12h
Meteo data	Air temperature (AT)	°C
	Relative humidity (RH)	%
	Wind speed (W)	(m/s)
Personal parameters setting	Age of person (y)	30
	Gender	Female
	Height (m)	1.65
	Weight (kg)	61.00
	Body position	Standing
	Walking speed	0.01

3. Results

The study examines the interaction between the design form of buildings and the climate parameters to enhance outdoor thermal comfort. The examination is performed via the implementation of three building typologies under identical climatic conditions in Guelma City, which is categorized as a semi-arid region. Highlighting the significant impact of the spatial organization of urban areas, especially during hot and cold periods, results are presented.

In-situ measurements were conducted within the study area using a dew point hygrometer and an anemometer, as mentioned in the meteorological data section. The objective is to establish an accurate database for the simulation process.

Following the results denoted in Fig. 5, comparing in-situ measurements of the study area in cold and hot periods, a negative correlation between AT and RH is revealed during the different time series. This signifies that, as AT increases, RH will be reduced.

Furthermore, diurnal temperature variations were also examined. The exhibition of the highest AT in both the summer and winter seasons was at 12 p.m., reaching up to 46°C in a hot period. Contrarily, RH peaked at 8 a.m. in both pe-

Figure 5. Comparison of in-situ measurement of the study area in cold and hot periods.

riods, reaching a maximum of 63.4% in hot periods and 75.2% in cold periods. Wind speed (W) generally remains low, with a maximum value reaching 1.95 m/s, whereas the cold period was more variable, with maximum values reaching 8 m/s.

In the hot period with vegetation masking (Table 4), the maximum AT is slightly lower than the hot period without vegetation (37.60°C Compared to 46°C). Relative humidity and wind speed also decreased with vegetation cover. Overall, the data indicates Guelma experiences hot and dry summers with low wind speeds, while winters are cooler with higher humidity and more variable winds, justifying the previous recorded levels.

Building upon the limitations discussed earlier in the software selection criteria section, considering in-situ measurements separately is deficient for a full comprehensive evaluation of thermal perception and the influence of urban design on achieving comfort. Consequently, simulation validation is needed. Therefore, this study utilized the collected data as input for the ENVI-met simulation of the modeled geometric configuration. To identify the most thermally comfortable outdoor environment, the simulation outputs of AT levels and distribution were analyzed based on key urban design factors encompassing building typology, street orientation, urban canyon, and vegetation presence. Tables 6–8 report the simulation results conducted using the ENVI-met software, considering both 2D and 3D configurations. The simulation status and

Table 6. Results of the first simulated building form (Scenario 1).

Spatial distribution		2d configuration		3d configuration			
Thermal distribution		AT 1.4 m height		AT 5 m height		AT 9 m height	
Hot-climate period	Simulation initialization						
	Simulation final run						
Cold-climate period	Simulation initialization						
	Simulation final run						

Table 7. Results of the second simulated building form (Scenario 2).

Spatial distribution		2d configuration	3d configuration		
Thermal distribution		AT 1.4 m height	AT 5 m height	AT 9 m height	
Hot-climate period	Simulation initialization	 min AT = 40.97°C max AT = 41.08°C			
	Simulation final run	 min AT = 36.25°C max AT = 37.67°C			
Cold-climate period	Simulation initialization	 min AT = 09.11°C max AT = 09.22°C			
	Simulation final run	 min AT = 09.89°C max AT = 11.81°C			

Table 8. Results of the third simulated building form (Scenario 3).

Spatial distribution		2d configuration	3d configuration	
Thermal distribution		AT 1.4 m height	AT 5 m height	AT 9 m height
Hot-climate period	Simulation initialization	 min AT = 19.85°C max AT = 39.56°C		
	Simulation final run	 min AT = 21.68°C max AT = 35.80°C		
Cold-climate period	Simulation initialization	 min AT = 09.08°C max AT = 19.85°C		
	Simulation final run	 min AT = 09.75°C max AT = 19.78°C		

period, as well as details on the name, timeframe, orientation, and thermal distribution height of each simulated spatial configuration, are indicated at the top right corner of each figure in the thermal distribution section.

Accordingly, the urban boundary layer (UBL) of the simulated built configurations is depicted in Table 9, presenting a comparative analysis of UBL under different built configurations across hot and cold periods. The results provided an additional demonstration of the influence of seasonal temperature variations and spatial patterns on outdoor comfort and the creation of urban heat islands. Denoted that the warmer colors indicate higher temperatures, while cooler colors represent lower temperatures.

Table 9. The urban boundary layer of the simulated built configurations.

Thermal distribution		
Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 3
Hot period		
<p>Scenario 1 Simulation 07.03.2024</p> <p>Potential Air Temperature 32.96 °C 33.28 °C 33.60 °C 33.92 °C 34.24 °C 34.56 °C 34.88 °C 35.20 °C 35.42 °C Min: 32.96 °C Max: 35.42 °C</p> <p>Wind Speed 2.00 m/s 4.00 m/s 6.00 m/s 8.00 m/s 10.00 m/s</p>	<p>Scenario 2 Simulation 25.03.2024</p> <p>Potential Air Temperature 35.12 °C 35.44 °C 35.76 °C 36.08 °C 36.40 °C 36.72 °C 37.04 °C 37.36 °C 37.68 °C 37.96 °C Min: 35.12 °C Max: 37.96 °C</p> <p>Wind Speed 2.00 m/s 4.00 m/s 6.00 m/s 8.00 m/s 10.00 m/s</p>	<p>Scenario 3 Simulation 22.04.2024</p> <p>Potential Air Temperature 34.53 °C 34.85 °C 35.17 °C 35.49 °C 35.81 °C 36.13 °C 36.45 °C 36.77 °C 37.09 °C 37.41 °C 37.73 °C 38.05 °C 38.37 °C 38.69 °C 39.01 °C 39.33 °C 39.65 °C 39.97 °C 40.29 °C 40.61 °C 40.93 °C 41.25 °C 41.57 °C 41.89 °C 42.21 °C 42.53 °C 42.85 °C 43.17 °C 43.49 °C 43.81 °C 44.13 °C 44.45 °C 44.77 °C 45.09 °C 45.41 °C 45.73 °C 46.05 °C 46.37 °C 46.69 °C 47.01 °C 47.33 °C 47.65 °C 47.97 °C 48.29 °C 48.61 °C 48.93 °C 49.25 °C 49.57 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<p>min AT = 32.96°C max AT = 35.42°C</p>	<p>min AT = 35.12°C max AT = 37.96°C</p>	<p>min AT = 34.53°C max AT = 36.73°C</p>
Cold period		
<p>Scenario 1 Simulation 25.03.2024</p> <p>Potential Air Temperature 10.26 °C 10.58 °C 10.90 °C 11.22 °C 11.54 °C 11.86 °C 12.18 °C 12.50 °C 12.82 °C 13.14 °C 13.46 °C 13.78 °C 14.10 °C 14.42 °C 14.74 °C 15.06 °C 15.38 °C 15.70 °C 16.02 °C 16.34 °C 16.66 °C 16.98 °C 17.30 °C 17.62 °C 17.94 °C 18.26 °C 18.58 °C 18.90 °C 19.22 °C 19.54 °C 19.86 °C 20.18 °C 20.50 °C 20.82 °C 21.14 °C 21.46 °C 21.78 °C 22.10 °C 22.42 °C 22.74 °C 23.06 °C 23.38 °C 23.70 °C 24.02 °C 24.34 °C 24.66 °C 24.98 °C 25.30 °C 25.62 °C 25.94 °C 26.26 °C 26.58 °C 26.90 °C 27.22 °C 27.54 °C 27.86 °C 28.18 °C 28.50 °C 28.82 °C 29.14 °C 29.46 °C 29.78 °C 30.10 °C 30.42 °C 30.74 °C 31.06 °C 31.38 °C 31.70 °C 32.02 °C 32.34 °C 32.66 °C 32.98 °C 33.30 °C 33.62 °C 33.94 °C 34.26 °C 34.58 °C 34.90 °C 35.22 °C 35.54 °C 35.86 °C 36.18 °C 36.50 °C 36.82 °C 37.14 °C 37.46 °C 37.78 °C 38.10 °C 38.42 °C 38.74 °C 39.06 °C 39.38 °C 39.70 °C 40.02 °C 40.34 °C 40.66 °C 40.98 °C 41.30 °C 41.62 °C 41.94 °C 42.26 °C 42.58 °C 42.90 °C 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°C 11.49 °C 11.61 °C 11.73 °C 11.85 °C 11.97 °C 12.09 °C 12.21 °C</p>	

These findings were confirmed by cold period simulation, where PAT reached almost 14°C compared to 11.65°C in the simulation initialization.

The results provided an additional demonstration of wind speed (W) measured at UHI layer $k = 3$ (1.4 m height from the ground) to below 2 m/s in the same courtyard, equivalent to in-situ measurements. The particular reason for this decrease can be linked to the building's closed form and the street canyon dimension (Chatzidimitriou and Yannas 2017). These two indicators created a microclimate with limited wind flow. The restricted airflow increases the potential for heat trapping, contributing to higher temperatures, especially during hot periods. While the building's north-south orientation minimized direct solar radiation, the limited air circulation led to a heat island effect within the courtyard.

The presence of vegetation cover, particularly the *Melia azedarach* trees, significantly mitigated the PAT at a higher elevation $k = 8$ (9 m in height). This reduction from 35.21°C to 34.52°C is likely attributable to the species' documented ability to alleviate heat stress (Benkouachi et al. 2022).

While sharing the same north-south orientation, the linear building typology (Scenario 2) exhibited a contrast in PAT and W distribution compared to Scenario 1. The dissimilarity is noticeable at 1.4 m of height, where the thermal sensation is perceived the most by the users of outer space.

The highest potential air temperature (PAT) recorded in scenario 1 is localized in the courtyard, as previously mentioned, while scenario 2 is concentrated in the northeastern part, reaching 36.96°C cut at 1.4 m from the ground. The observed differences in temperature readings at different heights within Scenario 2 can be attributed to the UHI effect and urban density. The temperature distribution appears to be relatively uniform, with a minimum of 35.39°C and a maximum of 36.96°C cut at 1.4 m. At 5 m in height, the temperature distribution is similar to the 1.4-m height, with a slight increase in the maximum temperature (37.54°C). At 9 m in height, the PAT distribution is still similar, but with a further increase up to 37.67°C. In addition, the generated temperatures at all measured heights appear to be higher compared to scenario 1. The location of scenario 2 in a densely built environment, previously mentioned in Fig. 3, characterized by material with a lower albedo factor (asphalt and concrete), creates impervious surfaces, leading to higher temperatures at different heights (Boukhabla et al. 2013).

A linear shape, creating a significantly wider street canyon compared to the more compact building form in scenario 1, characterizes scenario 2. This particular attribution allows more sunlight to reach the ground, similarly reported by (Limona et al. 2019), another factor explaining the previous observation. This factor also augments the exposure to air movement, which justifies the elevation in wind speed during cold winter in scenario 2 (up to 4 m/s in the area between buildings) while the wind flow rate stabilized at around 2 m/s in the hot period. The wider canyon provides a more open environment, potentially mitigating heat island effects and improving thermal comfort. The wider street canyon allows for better air circulation, which can help to dissipate heat and reduce temperatures. However, additional factors, such as vegetation, are essential. The absence of vegetation cover in scenario 2 limits its potential for mitigating heat.

Scenario 3 revealed completely different results from the pre-discussed scenarios. The east-west building orientation responded with a stable distribution

of potential air temperature (PAT) within the outdoor environment. The minimum and maximum air temperatures (AT) for Scenario 3 are within the same range as Scenarios 1 and 2, indicating similar overall thermal conditions. The PAT recorded ranging between 39.56°C and 39.87°C in the simulation initialization and 35.55°C and 35.80°C in the simulation final run. However, the built geometry resulted in less variation of temperature across the different facades of the building. This can contribute to direct exposure of the outdoor area surrounding the buildings to weather variations in both winter and summer seasons.

The urban boundary layer (UBL) mapping of the three simulated model results reinsured the significant contribution of the spaces between buildings to hold heat levels and cause heat stress, especially during hot periods when comfort is essential. In addition, the UBL mapping depicted PAT levels elevated as the position of the view plan differed in the hot period, which validated the mapping simulation results.

Based on the data presented, the north-south orientation appears to be the most advantageous when it comes to ensuring thermal comfort in a semi-arid climate, compared to the east-west building orientation, as it has been validated by Abdollahzadeh and Biloría (2021) and Abd Elraouf et al. (2022).

In terms of the spatial urban form, Scenario 1 appears to be the least beneficial scenario among the three simulated configurations for promoting outdoor thermal comfort in a hot period. The north-south orientation with courtyard configuration minimizes direct solar radiation, but still restricted airflow leads to heat trapping and higher temperatures, especially during hot periods, resulting in discomfort in areas frequently used by inhabitants. On the other hand, the courtyard urban configuration represents beneficial conditions, especially during the cold period. The linear building layout with a wider street canyon (Scenario 2) resulted in higher temperatures due to its urban texture; nevertheless, it improved air circulation compared to the more compact building layout (Scenario 1).

The study outcomes confirm the interplay between microclimatic data and urban design elements (form, orientation, surface albedo, and urban canyon) that significantly influence weather conditions in outdoor spaces (Güller and Toy 2024). Moreover, the necessity of appropriate urban planning and design that prioritizes green infrastructure is underscored (Abdelmejeed and Gruehn 2023). This recommendation is evidenced in Table 4, where a decrease of around 8°C in maximum (AT) is noticed in in-situ measurements conducted under the masking effect.

As the findings signified a generally decisive simulation process, a deviation up to 3°C between the initial climatological measured data (in-situ measurements) and the simulation results was denoted. This discrepancy is likely attributed to two main reasons: the ENVI-met scheme used and the simulation duration. Due to the limited meteorological data, a simple forcing scheme was chosen for the model initialization. While this approach was necessary, it may have contributed to the observed deviation. A full forcing scheme, which requires additional detailed data, including cloud amount, precipitation, and radiation levels, would have provided more accuracy. This assumption has been confirmed by (Ouyang et al. 2022) and (S. Liu et al. 2024). In addition, the duration of the simulation process was 10 hours of simulation, while ENVI-met of-

fers 24 hours of generation. Hence, a difference in temperatures was observed. Given the multiple indicators used and the deviation falling within an acceptable margin of error, it is unlikely that the overall conclusions are significantly impacted.

5. Conclusion

To summarize everything stated, the present study emphasizes the importance of climate-adaptive urban configuration to enhance outdoor comfort. The evaluation of the urban spatial configuration considered three common urban geometries in the urban planning of Guelma City, characterized by a semi-arid climate. The selected building typologies were analyzed using ENVI-met and compared to in-situ measurements.

Key findings:

- Increased potential air temperature (PAT) within the courtyard (Scenario 1) to 36°C, leading to discomfort. Wind flow (W) at pedestrian level (1.4 m height) decreased to below 2 m/s.
- The highest PAT of 37.67°C was recorded in the northeastern part of scenario 2 with a stable W at 2 m/s.
- Scenario 3 offered similar levels of PAT ranging between 39.56°C and 39.87°C in the simulation initialization and 35.55°C and 35.80°C in the simulation final run. However, it exhibited less variation in PAT across building facades, potentially leading to direct exposure to extreme temperatures throughout the year.
- PAT increased with higher measurement positions (k levels) during hot periods. For instance, scenario 2 showed a difference of 1.04°C between 1.4 m in height (k = 3) and 9 m in height (k = 8).
- In-situ measurements under the green masking effect significantly reduce AT of approximately 8°C, further confirmed at k = 9 in scenario 1, where a 0.69°C difference in PAT is noticed.
- A 3°C deviation between simulation and in-situ measurements was observed.
- Among the weather parameters analyzed, AT emerged as the most significant parameter to affect outdoor thermal perception.

The conducted analysis illustrates a clear influence of urban morphology on outdoor comfort. Building orientation, form, and street canyon geometry proved to be key factors affecting outer space's thermal performance. Urban green spaces are essential for mitigating heat island effects and enhancing thermal comfort. Although the study primarily focused on urban morphology, future research should investigate the implementation of urban cooling strategies such as reflective surfaces, cool roofs, and urban water features to reduce urban heat stress.

While the results of this study are specific to Guelma City, Algeria, their broader implications extend to other cities with similar climatic conditions. Mediterranean and arid regions, facing similar challenges to those in semi-arid regions, can adopt the recommendations outlined in this study to enhance thermal comfort, mitigate heat island effects, and promote urban sustainability. By adapting the specific recommendations to the unique characteristics of each

region, planners and designers can create more resilient and sustainable urban environments in these challenging climates.

In conclusion, the results underscored the necessity of a full consideration of urban patterns and their related aspects. From the most convenient orientation and accurate dimension of canyons to the selection of materials and vegetation. Optimized urban planning can minimize solar heat gain during peak hours, maximize natural ventilation, and enhance the livability of urban environments. By carefully considering these cohesive elements, a harmonious urban environment conducive to thermal comfort is achievable.

Furthermore, simulation results were generally consistent with in-situ measurements, although some discrepancies were observed. The simplified forcing scheme used in ENVI-met and the simulation duration may have contributed to these deviations. Therefore, the research recommends a further investigation to examine the efficacy of the ENVI-met full forcing scheme, particularly when conducting simulations over longer periods. This examination is expected to increase the accuracy of microclimate analysis using ENVI-met software.

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Additional information

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No conflict of interest was declared.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text or Supplementary Information.